

Mechanism of Reinforcement in High Modulus Rubber Composites Containing a Continuous Hard Phase

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ABSTRACT

A general method is proposed for evaluating the phase continuity of multi-phase composites. The modulus of the composites (E) is given by the combination of the parallel (E_U) and series (E_L) models,

$$E = kE_U + (1-k)E_L$$

where k is a unique and essential parameter to represent the magnitude of a continuous hard phase in the composites quantitatively. Theoretical and experimental methods to obtain the k values for real composites are offered. The new method was applied to high modulus rubber composites produced by the interstitial polymerization of the divinylbenzene monomer in isoprene rubber to make clear the relation between the phase continuity and the physical and mechanical properties.

INTRODUCTION

The general method of rubber reinforcement is the incorporation of solid filler particles into the matrix, which introduces the improvement of physical and mechanical properties of rubber. In the reinforcement by solid fillers, however, there exists an unavoidable restriction from the processing point of view that higher the reinforcing effect of fillers or higher the filler content, poorer the blending or mixing of compounds, resulting in the limitation of reinforcement for rubbers.

Reinforcement by the polymerization of monomer in rubber, in contrast with this, offers many advantages not only improved processing characteristics but the real possibility to control phase morphologies, consequently physical and mechanical properties of the system as we want.

The investigation to be described in this report is about the mechanism of reinforcement in high modulus rubber composites produced by the interstitial polymerization of the divinylbenzene (DVB) monomer within rubber. It is characteristic that as the polymerization and crosslinking of divinylbenzene and isoprene rubber (IR) proceed, a phase separation occurs between polyDVB and crosslinked IR phases, resulting in a multi-phase composite system to be the basis of high reinforcement of rubber, as will be shown later.

There are many reports in the literature concerning interpenetrating polymer networks (IPN's) which are closely related to the present composites (1-7). IPN's exhibit a two-phase morphology consisting of hard and soft phases and are believed that both phases are continuous and interpenetrating each other. One of the major problems pending, however, is that it is quite difficult to evaluate the phase continuity of the interpenetration quantitatively. This has made it difficult, as a result, to correlate structural and morphological information to physical and mechanical properties quantitatively.

The high modulus rubber composites consisting of a continuous hard phase have many interesting and useful properties, e.g. typical morphology, high modulus, specific stress-strain behaviour and highly energetic properties in thermodynamic aspects. It is the purpose of the present work to provide a new method to evaluate the phase continuity of multiphase composite system theoretically and experimentally.

EXPERIMENTAL SECTION

1. Materials

A commercial isoprene rubber was selected as the component for a soft phase (rubber) and the divinylbenzene monomer for a hard phase (plastic). The divinylbenzene monomer had the following analysis (determined by gas chromatography): m-DVB 41.9%, p-DVB 42.6%, ethylvinylbenzene 15.4%, diethylbenzene 0.1%.

2. Preparation of Composites

2.1 IR-DVB Composites. The IR-DVB composites were synthesized by thermal polymerization techniques. IR was dissolved into the DVB monomer and maintained overnight at room temperature so that a uniform distribution of monomer could be achieved through the sample, adding 1% by weight of dicumyl peroxide (DCPO) for cross-linking. Compounds were then mixed on a mill, sheeted off and cured in a compression molding operation at a temperature of 160°C for 30 min.

2.2 IR-polyDVB compounds. The IR-polyDVB compounds were prepared as a comparison with the IR-DVB composites. The powdered polyDVB of a diameter of 1-10µm which was separately polymerized thermally at 160°C for 30 min and mixed with IR on a mill, 1% by weight of DCPO being added, then cured similarly to the IR-DVB composites.

3. Measurements

3.1 Electron Microscopy. A modification of Kato's osmium tetroxide (OsO₄) staining technique (7,8) was used to prepare specimens for the microscope. The fully stained sections about 1µm³ were imbeded in the reaction product of methyl methacrylate and butyl methacrylate. The ultrathin specimens of 600-800Å were cut using a LKB Ultramicrotome. Electron micrographs were taken by the direct observation of the ultrathin sections employing a HU-11 transmission electron microscope of Hitach Seisakusho Co..

3.2 Mechanical Measurements.

(i) Tensile Measurements. Tensile properties of the composites were measured by Instron Universal Testing Machine with a crosshead speed of 5 cm/min at room temperature.

(ii) Dynamic Mechanical Spectroscopy. Measurements of the dynamic properties were carried out with a Viscoelastic Spectrometer of Iwamoto Seisakusho Ltd., Type VES-D, over a wide temperature range (-100°C ~ 150°C) at 110 Hz.

(iii) Force-Temperature Measurements. The automatic stress-relaxometer produced by The Great Giken Co., was used in this work. Specimens were elongated to the predetermined extension ratio at the highest temperature and allowed to relax for at least 5 hr until a steady force was obtained, a newly cut specimen being used for each extension. After the retractive force at the highest temperature is recorded, the temperature was lowered at intervals of 10°C and the force measured, the time required for thermal equilibrium at every temperature being reached within 30 min.. The temperature was then raised again in 10°C steps to the initial temperature. The values of retractive force in cooling and heating

processes were in good agreement with each other, which indicates the physical and chemical relaxation can be neglected during measurements.

RESULTS

1. Electron Microscopy

Typical electron micrograph of the IR-DVB composite of 36%DVB by volume ($\phi_{DVB} = \phi_H = 0.36$) is shown in Fig.1. The dark portion represents the osmium tetroxide stained IR phase, while the bright, the unstained polyDVB phase. There is seen a distinct phase separation between two components with a fine structure on the order of hundreds of angstroms and their cluster domains of around 1000\AA for both of polyDVB and IR. The domain size of the polyDVB increases as DVB content increases, but being independent of the peroxide content (not shown here).

Fig.1 Electron micrograph of the IR-DVB composite ($\phi_H=0.36$)

2. Stress-Strain Behaviour

The typical stress-strain curve for the IR-DVB composite ($\phi_H = 0.38$), small amounts of sulphur being added to improve the tensile properties, is shown in Fig.2, together with curves for the reinforced natural rubber containing 50 parts of carbon black and the polyurethane elastomer. It is characteristics of the IR-DVB composite to show an initial linear stress-strain relation up to 30 - 50% strain, consequently the vastly increased energy to rupture, which indicates the sufficient strength of the hard domains and their morphological structure under a cyclic deformation at small strain.

Fig.2. Typical stress-strain curves

3. Dynamic Mechanical Properties

The temperature dependence of dynamic storage moduli (E) is shown in Fig.3. The polyDVB ($\phi_H = 1.0$) does not show any apparent transition over a temperature range measured, which indicates the polyDVB consists of three dimensional tight gel where molecular movements are almost frozen. As DVB content increases, the E values for each composite above the glass transition temperature (T_g) are raised almost in parallel but the glass transition temperature itself is scarcely affected by the content of DVB. These observations may suggest that the polyDVB and rubber phases are separated each other distinctly.

4. Force-Temperature Relationship

The temperature coefficients of the retractive force at successive fixed lengths obtained for the IR-polyDVB compound ($\phi_H = 0.36$) and the IR-DVB composite ($\phi_H = 0.29$) are shown in Fig.4 and Fig.5, where the extension ratio, λ given refer to 20°C .

In the IR-polyDVB compound, the retractive force-temperature curves show negative slope at a small strain but positive at a large strain as usually well known in NR gum or the filler reinforced rubber (7 - 9). The IR-DVB composite, on the other hand, shows a negative temperature coefficient of the retractive force over a strain level measured.

Fig.3 Dynamic storage modulus for the IR-DVB composites as a function of temperature

With the data obtained above, thermodynamic treatments were performed to evaluate the ratio of the internal energy component (f_e) to the total retractive force (f), f_e/f .

For this purpose we employed the Flory-Hoeve-Ciferri equation (10) on the assumption that the rubber networks obey the modified Gaussian law, which has been utilized by most workers in obtaining the f_e/f values,

$$\frac{f_e}{f} = 1 - \frac{T}{f} \left(\frac{\partial f}{\partial T} \right)_{P,L} - \frac{3T\varepsilon}{\lambda^3 - 1} \quad (1)$$

where ε is the linear thermal expansion coefficient and T , P , L and λ the temperature, pressure, length and extension ratio respectively. The f_e/f values calculated with Eq.(1) are shown in Fig.6. It is generally seen that the f_e/f ratio decreases with increasing λ at first, then gradually levels off or decreases for the pure IR ($\phi_H = 0$) and the IR-polyDVB compounds ($\phi_H = 0.18$, $\phi_H = 0.36$), as usually shown in the rubber like materials mentioned before (7 - 9). For the IR-DVB composites, however, the f_e/f ratio rapidly decreases from the initial high value and increases again with increasing λ , passing through the minimum f_e/f of quite high magnitude. These phenomena clearly indicate that the IR-DVB composites are beyond the limits of the Gaussian law applicable to rubber like materials, which requires a new treatment for understanding the relation between the structure and properties of the high modulus rubber composites presented here.

DISCUSSION

1. Quantitative Analysis of the Phase Continuity in High Modulus Rubber Composites

It is not easy or sometimes impossible to judge the phase continuity of the system quantitatively from electron micrographs of two-dimensional plane. There is another method, however, to evaluate it by correlating the elastic modulus of the composites with the morphology of the system, and actually many theoretical equations have been proposed for this purpose (11 - 13). However, they are not necessarily practical for evaluating morphology of real composites quantitatively and relating the information thus obtained with their physical and mechanical properties. Because, most of these equations contain the parameters which are difficult to understand as an direct indication of the morphology changing with compositions, from one continuous to two continuous phases, then to one continuous phase again, for example. For the further analysis of the present results, therefore, we employed the new method, simple but more practical for evaluating the real composites.

Fig.7 exhibits plots of $\log E$ vs DVB contents (ϕ_H) read off on the curves in

Fig.4 Stress-temperature curves of the IR-polyDVB compound ($\phi_H=0.36$)

Fig.5 Stress-temperature curves of the IR-DVB composite ($\phi_H = 0.29$), cooling (\circ), heating (\bullet)

Fig.6 Relative energy contribution of the IR-DVB composites (—), together with the IR-polyDVB compounds (---), (Δ : $\phi_H = 0.18$, \bullet : 0.36)

Fig.3 at 20°C. The upper broken line (E_U) in the figure is calculated with Eq. (2), corresponding to the parallel model of hard (H) and soft (S) phases, while the lower broken line (E_L) calculated with Eq. (3), the series model of both phases,

$$E_U = \phi_H E_H + \phi_S E_S \quad (2)$$

$$E_L = \left(\frac{\phi_H}{E_H} + \frac{\phi_S}{E_S} \right)^{-1} \quad (3)$$

where E , E_H and E_S are the modulus of composite, hard and soft phases, respectively and ϕ_H and ϕ_S the volume fraction of both phases, $\phi_H + \phi_S = 1$.

It can be agreed that in real composite systems which have two continuous and other discontinuous phases, the modulus of the system must be the combination of the upper and lower bounds to the modulus, E_U and E_L , respectively. That is, the modulus of the composite can be given by the equation,

$$E = kE_U + (1-k)E_L \quad (4)$$

where k is a function to predict the contribution of a parallel model in the system, $0 \leq k \leq 1$. In such a case as $E_H/E_S \gg 1$, ($E_H/E_S > 10^3$ in the present system), Eq. (2) at $\phi_H = \phi_{H1}$ will be

$$E_{U1} \approx \phi_{H1} E_H \quad (5)$$

In addition, $E_U/E_L \gg 1$, ($E_U/E_L > 10^2$ in most compositions in the present system), then the modulus of the composite at $\phi_H = \phi_{H1}$ will be

$$E_1 \approx k \phi_{H1} E_H \quad (6)$$

on the other hand, the modulus E_1 at $\phi_H = \phi_{H2}$ on the upper line can be given

$$E_1 \approx \phi_{H2} E_H \quad (7)$$

combining Eq. (6) and Eq. (7),

$$k \approx \frac{\phi_{H2}}{\phi_{H1}} \quad (8)$$

The situations are schematically illustrated in Fig.8.

The parameter k thus obtained will now correspond to the volume fraction of a continuous hard phase in total hard content. That is, k is a unique and essential parameter to represent the magnitude of a continuous hard phase in the

composite, then to control the morphological, physical and mechanical properties of multi-phase system.

2. Phase Formation in the IR-DVB Composites evaluated with the k value

The quantity k obtained empirically are plotted against the volume fraction of a hard phase, ϕ_H in Fig.9 (filled circle). As would be expected, the k values strongly suggest the following changes in morphology as DVB content increases: At low concentrations of DVB ($\phi_H = 0 \sim 0.15$), the k value remains negligibly small, which predicts that polyDVB is dispersed as solid spheres in soft rubber. At 15% $\sim 30\%$ DVB, the k values start to increase gradually and reach around 0.07 at $\phi_H = 0.3$. Above the range of 30% DVB, the k values increase almost linearly up to 70% DVB, then approach unity with increasing DVB. It should be noted that $\phi_H = 0.3$ and $\phi_H = 0.7$ correspond to the volume fraction for the closest packing. The results thus obtained clearly indicate the aspect of the phase changes with composition for such composites made up of rigid plastic and soft rubber.

Presumably, however, there must be the questions that the modulus of the composites reinforced with carbon blacks or silicas are higher than that of calculated with the series model. That is, in spite of the cases that there do not exist a real continuous hard phase, the k values will be finite. As a comparison, therefore, the modulus E and k values obtained in the same manner for the IR-polyDVB compounds are shown in Fig.7 and Fig.9 (open circle) as a function of ϕ_H . Although the moduli for the IR-polyDVB compounds are considerably higher than the lower line for a series model in Fig.7, the absolute k values calculated with Eq.8 are negligibly small. This result means that in such a system $E_H/E_S \gg 1$, the contribution to the modulus from a discontinuous hard phase is so small that one can evaluate the modulus, then the morphology of the system by paying attention to a continuous hard phase only.

At the same time, however, the fact that the k values for the IR-polyDVB are not zero indicates the limitation of the present new method that it is difficult to judge a phase continuity accurately at the composition of quite low or quite high ϕ_H values, because the assumption used for obtaining Eq.6 is oversimplified at such compositions.

Anyway, however, it is apparent that the parameter k thus obtained can be a useful weapon for evaluating the phase continuity of the composites quantitatively, at least as a first approximation.

3. Evaluation of Force-Temperature Relation characterized with the k value

Thermodynamic treatments assuming the Gaussian law are not applicable to the present composites containing a continuous hard phase inside, as described before. However, since we have now constructed the new method to obtain the phase continuity quantitatively, then it has become possible to evaluate the force-temperature relations with the parameter k .

Generally, the temperature coefficient of the modulus (or retractive force) is given in Eq.(9)

Fig.7 Modulus (E) vs volume fraction of DVB (ϕ_H) at 20°C

Fig.8 Plots of $\log E$ vs ϕ_H (schematic)

for hard plastic(energetic) and in Eq.(10) for soft rubber(entropic),

$$E_H = E_H^0 - \alpha T \quad (9) \quad (14)$$

$$E_S = E_S^0 + \beta T \quad (10)$$

then, $\frac{\partial E_H}{\partial T} = -\alpha$, $\frac{\partial E_S}{\partial T} = \beta$ (11)

where E_H^0 and E_S^0 are the moduli at 0°K and α, β the coefficient.

Then, combining Eq.(2) and Eq.(11) for the parallel model,

$$\frac{\partial EU}{\partial T} = -\alpha \varphi_H + \beta \varphi_S \quad (12)$$

for the series model, with Eq.(3) and Eq.(11) assuming $E_H/E_S \gg 1$,

$$\frac{\partial EL}{\partial T} \approx \frac{\beta}{\varphi_S} \quad (13)$$

Therefore, the temperature coefficient of the present combination model with the parallel and series models through the parameter k is given, from Eq.(4),

$$\frac{\partial E}{\partial T} \approx -k\varphi_H\alpha + (k\varphi_S + \frac{1-k}{\varphi_S})\beta \quad (14)$$

If the parameter k correctly reflects the phase continuity of the system, the theoretical temperature coefficient given by Eq.(14) must be in agreement with that obtained by the experiments given in Fig.3.

The results obtained theoretically and experimentally over the temperature range far from the glass transition region, i.e. 40°C ~ 140°C are given in Table 1 for the IR-DVB composites, where the quantity of α and β are 30kg/cm²°c and 6 x 10⁻³ kg/cm²°c read from polyDVB ($\varphi_H = 1.0$) and IR($\varphi_H = 0$) in Fig.3 respectively. The agreement between the theoretical and experimental values is satisfactory, which leads us the conclusion that the combination model proposed here in terms of the parameter k is quite useful for understanding the multi-phase composites.

Table 1 Temperature coefficient ($\partial E/\partial T$) (kg/cm²·°c) for the IR-DVB composites

φ_H	Theoretical	Experimental
0.09	-1.50 x 10 ⁻³	-1.5 x 10 ⁻³
0.18	-6.77 x 10 ⁻²	-4.5 x 10 ⁻²
0.27	-3.24 x 10 ⁻¹	-3.2 x 10 ⁻¹
0.36	-1.49	-1.4
0.45	-4.31	-5.0
0.63	-12.3	-12

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Fig.9 The k values against φ_H

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